

Make your pitch: let's solve the question of third space titles

Colin Simpson

DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17845053>

Inconsistent titles for third space roles have plagued us for decades (Geis & Klaassen, 1972). While it may seem trivial whether we are called learning designer, education designer, instructional designer, eLearning advisor, or education technologist, the variability in these titles make it harder to communicate about these roles and ensure that educators who need help are able to find it easily from the right people.

What if everyone somehow agreed on a single term for each of our various roles? (Assuming that we maintain broad role types of learning designer, educational technologist, academic developer and the array of other third space positions)

For example: there are no more educational designers or instructional designers – only learning designers

The same for education or learning or whatever technologist. Somehow we settle on – educational technologist (for example).

The same for academic/faculty/education developer.

Would this make life easier? Why?

What would you prefer your title to be?

In this discussion activity, I encouraged participants to make a pitch for your preferred title and make a case for why we should adopt their preferred title.

Will it solve anything? Will it change anything? Who knows. At least we can have some fun with it.

Well, since I started this whole thing I guess it is only fair for me to provide the first offering.

EdAdvisor – a collective term for people working in the tertiary education third space to enable better learning and teaching by supporting educators specifically. EdAdvisors include learning designers, educational technologists, and academic developers (and all of the many, many variations of these titles).

EdAdvisor is a portmanteau of Educator and Advisor. This acknowledges the fact that EdAdvisors (or EdAd for short) are frequently educators in their own right, as well as recognising that they advise the educators they work with. *Advise* is an important part of this name, as it recognises expertise, and elevates EdAdvisors beyond “just support” staff. Providing support is still a key part of what EdAds do, but there can be an implication of a less equal relationship when it is part of the title.

Some may notice the similarity of EdAdvisor to Edvisor or TELedvisor(s). Given that I was part of the discussion where we first coined Edvisor, this is no coincidence. Now that the TELedvisors Network has been around for close to eight years, this term has some degree of “brand recognition” in the sector. I am proud to be a TELedvisor but I think EdAdvisor is clearer in communicating what these people do. Over the years, I have seen this (and edvisor) misspelled frequently and also mispronounced. It doesn’t roll off the tongue. (There are no plans to change TELedvisors branding to EdAdvisors – currently.)

The term EdAdvisor does not represent everyone in the third space, just a sub-group who share a common purpose and commonly work together. It encourages collaboration and shared understanding, and makes it easier to collectively describe us. Please consider using the term EdAdvisor in the future. Thank you.

Reflection

The identity question has vexed us in the third space for more than fifty years. I suspect that our two greatest barriers to consistency are the desire to have ownership of role titles, which is understandable but not always practical, and the tendency in the higher education sector to demand the perfect over the good. In the case of the latter, any title where a small exception might be found, even if only relevant to 1 in 1000 cases, is often automatically dismissed as unsuitable. Part of this process is going to have to involve acceptance that some people won’t get their personal preference in exchange for agreeing on titles which have the widest possible understanding and acceptance.

References

- Geis, G., & Klaassen, J. (1972). It’s a word, It’s a name, It’s ... an Educational Technologist. *Educational Technology*, 12(12), 20–22.
- Mitchell, K., Simpson, C., & Adachi, C. (2017). What’s in a name? The ambiguity and complexity of technology enhanced learning roles. In H. Partridge, K. Davis, & J. Thomas (Eds.), *Me, Us, IT! Proceedings ASCILITE2017: 34th International Conference of Innovation, Practice and Research in the use of Educational Technologies in Tertiary Education* (p. 449), ASCILITE. <http://2017conference.ascilite.org/program/whats-in-a-name-the-ambiguity-and-complexity-of-technology-enhanced-learning-roles/>

About the author

Colin Simpson

Deakin University

Colin is a convenor of the TELedvisors Network and Lecturer in Learning Futures at Deakin University.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2175-9118>